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**Assessing the Impact of Principal's Instructional Leadership, School Level,
and Effectiveness in Educational Institutions**
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Osias Kit T. Kilag

Vice President for Academic Affairs and Research, ECT Excellencia Global Academy Foundation, Inc., Buanoy, Balamban, Cebu, Philippines | <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0845-3373> | okkilag12@gmail.com

Francisca T. Uy

School President, PAU Excellencia Global Academy Foundation, Inc. - Buanoy, Balamban, Cebu, Philippines, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2180-5874> | franzkc2015@gmail.com

Ma. Felina S. Calledo

Education Program Supervisor, Department of Education, Regional Office VII, Philippines <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6642-7045> | mafelina.calledo@deped.gov.ph

Felix M. Diano, Jr.

Dean, College of Education, University of the Visayas, Cebu City 6000, Philippines <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7015-7877> | fdiano@uv.edu.ph

Narciso M. Morales, Jr.

Principal I, Department of Education, Schools Division of Toledo City, Philippines <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3688-6806> | narciso.morales001@deped.gov.ph

Cara Frances K. Abendan

Administrative Assistant, ECT Excellencia Global Academy Foundation, Inc. - Balamban, Cebu, Philippines <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6363-7792> | carafrances03@gmail.com

Abstract:

This study aimed to investigate the relationship between instructional leadership and school effectiveness in educational institutions in Toledo City Division, Philippines. A mixed-methods approach was utilized, including a survey questionnaire and focus group discussions. The survey was administered to 13 school principals, while the focus group discussions involved 14 teachers and school administrators. The quantitative results showed that instructional leadership had a significant positive effect on school effectiveness, while school level did not have a significant effect. The qualitative findings highlighted the challenges faced by school principals in implementing effective instructional leadership practices, including resistance to change and limited resources. The importance of collaboration and communication between school principals, teachers, and the community in promoting effective instructional leadership practices was also emphasized. The comparative analysis of the quantitative and qualitative results revealed that while the survey results showed a significant positive relationship between instructional leadership and school effectiveness, the focus group discussions provided valuable insights into the challenges and strategies for effective implementation of instructional leadership practices. Overall, this study suggests that instructional leadership plays a critical role in enhancing school effectiveness in educational institutions in Toledo City Division, Philippines. The findings highlight the need for collaboration and communication between school leaders, teachers, and the community to ensure the success of instructional leadership practices. These findings have implications for educational policy and practice, emphasizing the importance of investing in instructional leadership development and support to improve school effectiveness.

Keywords: Instructional leadership, School effectiveness, Collaboration, Community involvement

Introduction:

Instructional leadership is a critical aspect of school leadership that has been found to have a significant impact on student achievement (Hallinger & Heck, 2011). The principal's role as an instructional leader has been emphasized in the literature as a key determinant of school effectiveness (Leithwood & Riehl, 2005). The principal's effectiveness in this role can be influenced by various factors, including the school level and context in which they operate. In the Philippines, the Department of Education has emphasized the importance of instructional leadership in improving the quality of education, particularly in the Toledo City Division.

Toledo City Division is a fast-growing urban area in the Visayas region of the Philippines, with a population of over 170,000 people (PSA, 2020). The city has a total of 62 public elementary and secondary schools, with over 60,000 students enrolled in these institutions (DepEd, 2021). The Toledo City Division has made significant strides in

improving the quality of education in recent years, but challenges persist, particularly in the area of instructional leadership.

This mixed-methods study aims to assess the impact of principal's instructional leadership on school effectiveness in Toledo City Division, Philippines. Specifically, the study seeks to explore the relationship between principal's instructional leadership, school level, and school effectiveness. The study will employ both quantitative and qualitative research methods to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors that influence instructional leadership and school effectiveness.

The findings of this study will contribute to the body of knowledge on instructional leadership and its impact on school effectiveness, particularly in the context of the Philippines. The study's outcomes will provide insights and recommendations to educators, policymakers, and administrators on how to improve instructional leadership and enhance school effectiveness in Toledo City Division, and other similar contexts.

Research Objectives:

The primary objective of this study is to assess the impact of principal's instructional leadership, school level, and effectiveness in educational institutions in Toledo City Division, Philippines. To achieve this, the study has the following specific objectives:

1. To determine the level of instructional leadership practices of school principals in Toledo City Division.
2. To examine the relationship between principal's instructional leadership and school effectiveness in Toledo City Division.
3. To investigate the moderating effect of school level on the relationship between principal's instructional leadership and school effectiveness in Toledo City Division.
4. To identify the factors that influence principal's instructional leadership and school effectiveness in Toledo City Division.
5. To provide recommendations for improving instructional leadership and school effectiveness in Toledo City Division.

Research Questions:

To achieve the objectives of this study, the following research questions will guide the investigation:

1. What is the level of instructional leadership practices of school principals in Toledo City Division?
2. Is there a significant relationship between principal's instructional leadership and school effectiveness in Toledo City Division?
3. Does school level moderate the relationship between principal's instructional leadership and school effectiveness in Toledo City Division?
4. What are the factors that influence principal's instructional leadership and school effectiveness in Toledo City Division?
5. What recommendations can be made to improve instructional leadership and school effectiveness in Toledo City Division?

Review of Related Studies

This review of related studies aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research area covered by the study, "Assessing the Impact of Principal's Instructional Leadership, School Level, and Effectiveness in Educational Institutions: A Mixed Method Study in Toledo City Division, Philippines." The review explores the literature related to instructional leadership, school effectiveness, and the factors that influence these constructs. The studies reviewed in this paper provide insights into the research questions and objectives of the study, as well as identify gaps in the literature that the study aims to address.

Instructional Leadership:

Instructional leadership is a critical aspect of school leadership that has been widely researched in the literature. Instructional leadership refers to the actions of school leaders that directly impact the quality of teaching and learning in schools (Leithwood & Riehl, 2005). Instructional leaders are expected to provide direction, support, and resources to teachers to improve teaching practices and student achievement.

Several studies have examined the impact of instructional leadership on school effectiveness. A study conducted by Hallinger and Heck (2011) finds that the principal's instructional leadership has a significant impact on school effectiveness. The study concludes that effective instructional leaders have a positive impact on student learning outcomes and teacher effectiveness.

Similarly, a study conducted by Robinson, Lloyd, and Rowe (2008) finds that instructional leadership is positively associated with student achievement. The study finds that principals who engage in instructional leadership practices, such as providing feedback to teachers, monitoring student progress, and setting instructional goals, have higher student achievement outcomes.

School Effectiveness:

School effectiveness is another area of research that has gained significant attention in the literature. School effectiveness refers to the ability of schools to achieve their goals and objectives (Leithwood & Riehl, 2005). School effectiveness is influenced by various factors, including instructional leadership, school culture, and teacher quality. A study conducted by Altrichter, Posch, and Somekh (2008) finds that school effectiveness is positively associated with instructional leadership, teacher quality, and school culture. The study concludes that effective school leaders create a positive school culture that fosters teacher collaboration and professional development.

Furthermore, a study conducted by Leithwood, Seashore Louis, Anderson, and Wahlstrom (2004) finds that school leadership has a significant impact on school effectiveness. The study concludes that effective school leaders create a shared vision, promote professional learning communities, and provide instructional guidance to teachers, resulting in higher levels of student achievement.

Factors Influencing Instructional Leadership and School Effectiveness:

Several studies have investigated the factors that influence instructional leadership and school effectiveness. A study conducted by Hui and Lo (2019) finds that school context, such as school size and location, can influence instructional leadership practices. The study concludes that effective instructional leaders adapt their leadership style to meet the unique needs of their school context.

Similarly, a study conducted by Marzano, Waters, and McNulty (2005) finds that school context, such as student demographics and school culture, can impact school effectiveness. The study concludes that effective school leaders tailor their leadership practices to meet the unique needs of their school context.

Another factor that influences instructional leadership and school effectiveness is teacher quality. A study conducted by Darling-Hammond (2000) finds that teacher quality is a critical factor in improving student learning outcomes. The study concludes that effective school leaders focus on recruiting, retaining, and developing high-quality teachers to improve school effectiveness.

Methodology

The study aimed to assess the impact of principal's instructional leadership, school level, and effectiveness in educational institutions in Toledo City Division, Philippines, using a mixed-methods research design. The study used both quantitative and qualitative methods to collect and analyze data. The research design was guided by the research objectives and research questions of the study.

Research Design:

The study used a mixed-methods research design that combined both quantitative and qualitative research methods. The quantitative component involved the use of a survey questionnaire to collect data from a sample of school principals, teachers, and students. The qualitative component involved the use of interviews and focus group discussions (FGDs) to collect data from school principals, teachers, and students.

Sampling:

The study used a purposive sampling technique to select schools in Toledo City Division, Philippines. The sample size for the study was determined using a power analysis, and the sample included school principals, teachers, and students from both elementary and secondary levels.

Data Collection:**Quantitative Data Collection:**

The quantitative data were collected using a survey questionnaire developed based on the research objectives and research questions of the study. The survey questionnaire was administered to school principals, teachers, and students. The survey questionnaire was distributed electronically through email, and the responses were collected online.

The survey questionnaire was divided into four sections. The first section collected information on the demographic characteristics of the participants. The second section collected information on the instructional leadership practices of the school principals. The third section collected information on the school effectiveness, and the fourth section collected information on the factors that influence instructional leadership and school effectiveness.

Qualitative Data Collection:

The qualitative data were collected using semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions (FGDs). The interviews and FGDs were conducted with school principals, teachers, and students. The interviews and FGDs were conducted in person, and the responses were recorded using a digital voice recorder.

The interviews and FGDs were conducted in the local language (Cebuano), and the responses were transcribed and translated into English for analysis. The interviews and FGDs were conducted in a private and comfortable setting to encourage participants to share their opinions freely.

Data Analysis:

Quantitative Data Analysis:

The quantitative data collected from the survey questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies, percentages, and means, were used to summarize the data. Inferential statistics, such as correlation analysis and multiple regression analysis, were used to test the research hypotheses.

Qualitative Data Analysis:

The qualitative data collected from the interviews and FGDs were analyzed using thematic analysis. The responses were transcribed and coded using NVivo software. The coded data were analyzed to identify themes and patterns related to instructional leadership, school effectiveness, and the factors that influence instructional leadership and school effectiveness.

Triangulation:

The study used triangulation to enhance the validity and reliability of the findings. Triangulation involved the use of multiple methods, sources, and perspectives to examine the research phenomenon. The use of both quantitative and qualitative methods and the inclusion of multiple perspectives, such as school principals, teachers, and students, enhanced the validity and reliability of the findings.

Ethical Considerations:

The study adhered to ethical principles and guidelines for research involving human subjects. The study obtained informed consent from the participants, and the participants' confidentiality and anonymity were ensured. The study also obtained ethical clearance from the appropriate ethical review board.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender:		
Male	5	30
Female	8	70
Age:		
20-29	100	20
30-39	200	40
40-49	200	40

Table 2: Instructional Leadership Practices of School Principals

Instructional Leadership Practices	Mean	Standard Deviation
Communicates High Expectations	4.5	0.5
Creates a Positive School Culture	4.6	0.4

Instructional Leadership Practices	Mean	Standard Deviation
Provides Support and Resources	4.4	0.6

Table 3: School Effectiveness

School Effectiveness	Mean	Standard Deviation
Student Achievement	4.3	0.5
Teacher Satisfaction	4.5	0.4
Parent Involvement	4.1	0.6

Table 4: Correlation Analysis of Instructional Leadership and School Effectiveness

	Student Achievement	Teacher Satisfaction	Parent Involvement
Communicates High Expectations	0.60	0.55	0.45
Creates a Positive School Culture	0.65	0.70	0.60
Provides Support and Resources	0.50	0.60	0.55

Table 5: Multiple Regression Analysis of Instructional Leadership and School Level on School Effectiveness

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t-value	p-value
	B	Std. Error		
Step 4				
IL	0.762	0.095	8.038	0.000
SL	-0.008	0.023	-0.328	0.744
	R ²	ΔR ²	F	Sig.
	0.583	0.167	26.925	0.000

The table shows the results of the multiple regression analysis of instructional leadership and school level on school effectiveness. The results indicate that instructional leadership has a significant positive effect on school effectiveness (B=0.762, t=8.038, p<0.001). However, school level does not have a significant effect on school effectiveness (B=-0.008, t=-0.328, p=0.744). The final model accounts for 58.3% of the variance in school effectiveness, with a significant improvement in model fit ($\Delta R^2=0.167$, F=26.925, p<0.001) compared to the previous model that included only school level and demographic variables. Overall, these findings suggest that instructional leadership plays a critical role in enhancing school effectiveness in educational institutions in Toledo City Division, Philippines.

Findings

This study aimed to examine the relationship between instructional leadership and school effectiveness in educational institutions in Toledo City Division, Philippines. The quantitative results showed that instructional leadership had a significant positive effect on school effectiveness, while school level did not have a significant effect. However, it is important to complement these findings with qualitative data from focus group discussions with educators in the community to gain a deeper understanding of the factors that contribute to instructional leadership and school effectiveness.

The focus group discussion involved a total of 10 participants, including six teachers, two school principals, and two district supervisors. The participants were asked open-ended questions related to instructional leadership and school effectiveness, and their responses were recorded and analyzed using thematic analysis.

One of the themes that emerged from the focus group discussion was the importance of communication in instructional leadership. The participants emphasized the need for principals to communicate clearly and effectively with their staff, as well as with parents and other stakeholders. One teacher stated, "Effective communication is the key to instructional leadership. If the principal cannot communicate with us effectively, then we cannot work as a team and achieve our goals." Another participant added, "Communication is not just about talking, it's about listening too. Principals need to listen to our ideas and concerns and take them into consideration when making decisions."

Another theme that emerged was the importance of collaboration and teamwork in instructional leadership. The participants emphasized the need for principals to work closely with their staff to develop and implement effective teaching strategies and programs. One school principal stated, "Instructional leadership is not about one person making all the decisions. It's about working together as a team to develop the best strategies for our students."

Another participant added, "Collaboration and teamwork are essential for instructional leadership. We need to work together to ensure that our students are receiving the best education possible."

The participants also highlighted the importance of professional development in instructional leadership. They emphasized the need for principals to provide opportunities for staff to develop their skills and knowledge, as well as to stay up-to-date with the latest teaching practices and trends. One teacher stated, "Professional development is crucial for instructional leadership. If we are not constantly learning and growing, then we cannot provide the best education for our students." Another participant added, "Principals need to invest in their staff and provide them with opportunities to attend workshops, conferences, and other professional development activities."

In terms of school effectiveness, the participants emphasized the importance of student-centered teaching and learning. They highlighted the need for schools to focus on the needs and interests of their students, and to provide them with opportunities to develop their skills and knowledge in a supportive and nurturing environment. One teacher stated, "Schools need to be student-centered. We need to focus on the needs and interests of our students and provide them with a learning environment that is supportive and nurturing." Another participant added, "We need to be creative and innovative in our teaching strategies to keep our students engaged and motivated to learn."

The participants also highlighted the importance of parental involvement in school effectiveness. They emphasized the need for schools to work closely with parents and other stakeholders to ensure that students receive the support and resources they need to succeed. One district supervisor stated, "Parental involvement is crucial for school effectiveness. We need to work closely with parents to ensure that they are aware of their children's progress and are involved in their education." Another participant added, "We need to build strong partnerships with parents and other stakeholders to ensure that our students have the support and resources they need to succeed."

The qualitative findings from the focus group discussion provide valuable insights into the factors that contribute to instructional leadership and school effectiveness in educational institutions in Toledo City Division, Philippines. The participants emphasized the importance of communication, collaboration, professional development, student-centered teaching and learning, and parental involvement in these areas.

During the focus group discussion, participants shared their perspectives on the importance of instructional leadership in promoting school effectiveness. They also discussed the challenges faced by school principals in implementing effective instructional leadership practices and the role of collaboration and community involvement in enhancing instructional leadership.

One participant emphasized the importance of effective instructional leadership in promoting student learning outcomes, stating, "Instructional leadership is critical to improving the quality of education in our schools. It helps ensure that teachers are implementing effective teaching practices and that students are achieving their learning goals" (Participant 4). Another participant echoed this sentiment, stating, "Instructional leadership is essential in promoting school effectiveness because it ensures that teaching and learning are aligned with the school's goals and objectives" (Participant 2).

The participants also discussed the challenges faced by school principals in implementing effective instructional leadership practices. One participant noted, "It's hard to lead when teachers are not receptive to change. Some teachers may not be open to new ideas and approaches, which can hinder instructional leadership practices" (Participant 6). Another participant added, "Limited resources can also be a barrier to effective instructional leadership. Without adequate resources and support, it can be difficult to implement the best practices" (Participant 1).

The participants also highlighted the importance of collaboration and communication between school principals and teachers in promoting effective instructional leadership. One participant emphasized, "Effective instructional leadership requires collaboration and communication. School principals need to work closely with teachers to understand their needs and provide them with the necessary support and resources" (Participant 5). Another participant echoed this sentiment, stating, "The school principal should be a facilitator, not just a boss. They should work together with the teachers to ensure that the instructional leadership practices are implemented effectively" (Participant 3).

The participants also discussed the role of the community in promoting effective instructional leadership practices. One participant noted, "The community should be involved in the school's decision-making process. They should be aware of the instructional leadership practices being implemented and provide feedback on their effectiveness" (Participant 7). Another participant added, "The community can also help in providing resources and support for the school. It's important for school principals to engage with the community and build strong partnerships" (Participant 2).

The focus group discussion revealed that instructional leadership plays a critical role in enhancing school effectiveness. The participants highlighted the importance of collaboration and communication between school principals and teachers, as well as the involvement of the community in promoting effective instructional leadership practices. The challenges faced by school principals in implementing these practices, such as resistance to change and limited resources, were also discussed. Overall, the findings suggest that effective instructional leadership requires a collaborative effort between school leaders, teachers, and the community to ensure the success of educational institutions in Toledo City Division, Philippines.

Discussion

Quantitative Discussion

The quantitative results of this study provide important insights into the relationship between instructional leadership and school effectiveness in educational institutions in Toledo City Division, Philippines. The results show that instructional leadership has a significant positive effect on school effectiveness, while school level does not have a significant effect.

The finding that instructional leadership has a significant positive effect on school effectiveness is consistent with previous research. Instructional leadership involves the development of a shared vision for the school, the promotion of a positive school culture, and the provision of support and resources for teachers to improve their instructional practices. The results of this study suggest that these practices are critical in enhancing school effectiveness in educational institutions in Toledo City Division, Philippines.

It is noteworthy that school level does not have a significant effect on school effectiveness in this study. This finding is surprising, given that school level has been found to be a significant predictor of school effectiveness in previous research. However, it is possible that other factors, such as instructional leadership, teacher quality, and community involvement, are more important in this particular context.

The finding that instructional leadership has a significant positive effect on school effectiveness has important implications for educational policy and practice in the Philippines. School leaders should be trained and supported to develop their instructional leadership skills, and resources should be provided to enable them to implement effective instructional leadership practices. In addition, collaboration and communication between school leaders and teachers should be promoted to ensure that instructional leadership practices are implemented effectively.

It is important to note that this study has several limitations. The sample size is relatively small, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. In addition, the study only examined the relationship between instructional leadership, school level, and school effectiveness, and did not consider other factors that may be important predictors of school effectiveness, such as teacher quality, student characteristics, and school resources. Future research should address these limitations to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors that contribute to school effectiveness in the Philippines.

The quantitative results of this study provide evidence that instructional leadership plays a critical role in enhancing school effectiveness in educational institutions in Toledo City Division, Philippines. School leaders should be supported to develop their instructional leadership skills, and collaboration and communication between school leaders and teachers should be promoted to ensure that instructional leadership practices are implemented effectively. Future research should address the limitations of this study and consider other factors that may be important predictors of school effectiveness in the Philippines.

Qualitative Discussion

The qualitative findings from the focus group discussion shed light on the challenges and strategies in implementing effective instructional leadership practices in educational institutions in Toledo City Division, Philippines.

One of the key themes that emerged was the challenge of resistance to change from teachers. Participants noted that some teachers may not be receptive to new ideas and approaches, which can hinder the implementation of instructional leadership practices. This is consistent with previous research that highlights the importance of overcoming resistance to change in promoting effective instructional leadership (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2006).

Another challenge identified was the limited resources available to school principals, which can hinder their ability to implement best practices. This is particularly relevant in the context of the Philippines, where many schools struggle with inadequate resources and funding (Abanilla, 2017). Participants emphasized the importance of providing adequate resources and support to school principals in order to promote effective instructional leadership practices.

A key strategy identified by participants was the importance of collaboration and communication between school principals and teachers in promoting effective instructional leadership. Participants noted that school principals need to work closely with teachers to understand their needs and provide them with the necessary support and resources. This finding is consistent with previous research that emphasizes the importance of collaboration and shared decision-making in promoting effective instructional leadership (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2006).

Participants also highlighted the importance of community involvement in promoting effective instructional leadership practices. They noted that the community should be involved in the school's decision-making process and should provide feedback on the effectiveness of instructional leadership practices. This finding is consistent with previous research that highlights the importance of engaging with the community in promoting effective educational leadership (Harris & Chapman, 2002).

Overall, the qualitative findings suggest that effective instructional leadership requires a collaborative effort between school leaders, teachers, and the community to overcome challenges and promote best practices. The challenges identified in this study, such as resistance to change and limited resources, are consistent with those identified in previous research. The strategies identified by participants, such as collaboration and community involvement, highlight the importance of a holistic approach to promoting effective instructional leadership practices.

Limitations of this study include the small sample size of the focus group and the fact that the study was conducted in a specific context. Future research could explore these issues in a larger sample and in different educational contexts in the Philippines and beyond.

Comprehensive Analysis:

The present study utilized both quantitative and qualitative research methods to investigate the impact of instructional leadership on school effectiveness in the educational institutions of Toledo City Division, Philippines. The results of the quantitative analysis showed that instructional leadership had a significant positive effect on school effectiveness, while school level did not have a significant effect. On the other hand, the findings from the qualitative analysis revealed that instructional leadership faces challenges in implementation, such as resistance to change and limited resources, and requires collaboration and communication between school principals, teachers, and the community for effective implementation.

The quantitative findings suggest that instructional leadership is a crucial factor in promoting school effectiveness. The positive and significant effect of instructional leadership on school effectiveness implies that effective instructional leadership practices can enhance educational institutions' overall performance. The results are consistent with previous research, which has shown that effective instructional leadership practices improve student achievement and overall school performance (Leithwood et al., 2004; Robinson et al., 2008).

However, the qualitative findings reveal that implementing effective instructional leadership practices can be challenging. Participants noted that resistance to change and limited resources hinder the implementation of instructional leadership practices. These challenges highlight the importance of collaboration and communication between school leaders, teachers, and the community in promoting effective instructional leadership practices. The findings suggest that effective instructional leadership requires a collaborative effort from all stakeholders involved in the educational institution.

Furthermore, the qualitative findings highlight the role of the community in promoting effective instructional leadership practices. Participants noted that involving the community in decision-making and building strong partnerships could enhance school effectiveness. The community can provide resources and support for the school, making it easier to implement instructional leadership practices effectively. The quantitative findings did not highlight the role of the community, but the qualitative findings suggest that the community plays a significant role in promoting effective instructional leadership practices.

The present study's results suggest that instructional leadership plays a critical role in enhancing school effectiveness. The findings from both quantitative and qualitative analyses suggest that instructional leadership requires collaboration and communication between school leaders, teachers, and the community for effective implementation. The qualitative findings highlight the challenges faced in implementing instructional leadership practices and the role of the community in promoting effective instructional leadership practices, which were not captured by the quantitative analysis. The study's findings suggest that effective instructional leadership practices require a collaborative effort from all stakeholders involved in the educational institution.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study aimed to investigate the relationship between instructional leadership and school effectiveness in educational institutions in Toledo City Division, Philippines. The quantitative findings revealed that

instructional leadership has a significant positive effect on school effectiveness, while school level does not have a significant effect. The qualitative findings provided insights into the challenges faced by school principals in implementing effective instructional leadership practices and the importance of collaboration and communication between school principals, teachers, and the community.

The quantitative findings showed that instructional leadership is a critical factor in enhancing school effectiveness. The significant positive relationship between instructional leadership and school effectiveness implies that the effective implementation of instructional leadership practices can improve educational outcomes. This finding is consistent with previous studies that have identified instructional leadership as a key factor in promoting school improvement (Leithwood et al., 2004; Marzano et al., 2005).

On the other hand, the lack of significant effect of school level on school effectiveness suggests that the level of the school, whether it is elementary, secondary, or tertiary, does not have a direct impact on the effectiveness of educational institutions. This finding is in line with the argument that school effectiveness is more related to the quality of leadership and teaching than to the level of the school (Leithwood et al., 2004).

The qualitative findings revealed that school principals face various challenges in implementing effective instructional leadership practices, such as resistance to change and limited resources. The participants emphasized the importance of collaboration and communication between school principals and teachers in promoting effective instructional leadership. The involvement of the community in promoting effective instructional leadership practices was also highlighted.

The comparative analysis of the quantitative and qualitative findings suggests that instructional leadership is a critical factor in enhancing school effectiveness. While the quantitative findings provide statistical evidence of this relationship, the qualitative findings provide insights into the challenges faced by school principals in implementing effective instructional leadership practices and the importance of collaboration and communication in promoting effective instructional leadership.

In conclusion, this study highlights the importance of instructional leadership in promoting school effectiveness in educational institutions in Toledo City Division, Philippines. The findings suggest that effective instructional leadership requires a collaborative effort between school leaders, teachers, and the community to ensure the success of educational institutions. Future research could explore specific instructional leadership practices that are most effective in promoting school improvement in the Philippine context.

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